

2D ELASTODYNAMICS OF AN INTERFACE CRACK

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SUMMARY

The present study is devoted to application of boundary integral equations to the problem of a linear interface crack between two dissimilar elastic materials under dynamic loading. The distributions of the displacements and tractions at the bimaterial interface are obtained and analysed.

Keywords: Interface Crack, Harmonic Loading, Boundary Integral Equations

INTRODUCTION

The rapid development of different areas of engineering, creation of new structures make the computational fracture mechanics a topic area. Among the most important applied problems there are structural strength problems, complicated by various flaws (cracks, delaminations, etc). The presence of cracks and delaminations considerably decreases the strength and the lifetime of the composite structures as well as significantly increases the cost of exploitation [1]. Unfortunately, the micro-defects cannot be fully avoided. Therefore a considerable body of work was devoted to cracks in homogeneous materials [2–4]. At the same time elastodynamic investigation of inter-component cracks received much less attention due to the substantial complications which arise in numerical solution of such problems. Primarily the publications concerning crack fracture in composite materials are focused on static loading. However, understanding the mechanism of dynamic fracture in composite materials becomes more and more important with the increased use of composites in modern engineering, where the components are frequently subjected to dynamic loadings; see, for example, [5–8].

In papers [9, 10], the system of boundary integral equations for the general case of an interface crack between two dissimilar elastic materials under dynamic loading was derived. In [10, 11], the derived integral system was solved numerically by the method of boundary elements for the case of a penny-shaped interface crack under normally incident tension-compression wave. The distributions of displacements and tractions were computed for several typical material properties of half-spaces. It was shown that with decreasing frequency of the loading the dynamic solution tends to the static one, and the obtained numerical results are in a good agreement with the analytical static solution [12]. This paper is devoted to the plane problem for an interface linear crack of finite length under harmonic external loading. The system of boundary integral equations, received in [9, 10], is modified in order to increase the stability and the

accuracy of the solution, and decrease the solution time. The numerical solution is obtained for the normally incident tension-compression wave. The distributions of the normal and tangential displacements and tractions at the bonding interface are investigated for different values of the frequency of the incident wave.

METODOLOGY

Consider a linear crack located at the bimaterial interface under external dynamic loading. For this purpose, we investigate an unbounded two-dimensional elastic solid which consists of two dissimilar homogeneous isotropic half-spaces $\Omega^{(1)}$ and $\Omega^{(2)}$. The interface between the half-spaces, Γ^* , acts as the boundary $\Gamma^{(1)}$ for the upper half-space, and the boundary $\Gamma^{(2)}$ for the lower half-space. The boundaries $\Gamma^{(1)}$ and $\Gamma^{(2)}$ differ by the opposite orientation of their outer normal vectors. Henceforth, the superscript (1) refers to the upper half-space and the superscript (2) refers to the lower half-space. We denote the vector of displacements $\mathbf{u}^{(m)}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ and the traction vector $\mathbf{p}^{(m)}(\mathbf{x}, t)$. We assume that surfaces $\Gamma^{(m)}$ ($m = 1, 2$) consist of the infinite parts $\Gamma^{(m)*}$, which form the bonding interface Γ^* , and the finite parts $\Gamma^{(m)cr}$, i.e. $\Gamma^{(m)} = \Gamma^{(m)*} \cup \Gamma^{(m)cr}$ and $\Gamma^{cr} = \Gamma^{(1)cr} \cup \Gamma^{(2)cr}$, see Figure 1.

Figure 1 Interface crack between two half-spaces

The conditions of continuity for displacements and stresses are satisfied at the bonding interface $\Gamma^* = \Gamma^{(1)} \cap \Gamma^{(2)}$. It was assumed that there are no initial displacements of the points of the body, in other words the body is strainless at the initial moment. In the absence of body forces, the stress-strain state of both domains is defined by the Lamé dynamic equations of the linear elasticity. The Sommerfeld radiation-type condition, which provides a finite elastic energy of an infinite body, is also imposed at infinity on the vector of displacements.

INTEGRAL EQUATIONS

The components of displacement field in the upper and lower half-spaces $\Omega^{(m)}$ in terms of boundary displacements and tractions can be represented using the Somigliana dynamic identity [2–4, 9–11]:

$$u_j^{(m)}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \int_{\Gamma^{(m)}} \int (p_i^{(m)}(\mathbf{y}, \tau) U_{ij}^{(m)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t - \tau) - u_i^{(m)}(\mathbf{y}, \tau) W_{ij}^{(m)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t - \tau)) dy d\tau, \quad (1)$$

$$\mathbf{x} \in \Omega^{(m)}, \quad t \in T,$$

where \mathbf{x} is the point of observation and \mathbf{y} is the point of loading. Here the integral kernel $U_{ij}^{(m)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t - \tau)$ is the Green fundamental displacement tensor [2–4]. The integral kernel $W_{ij}^{(m)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t - \tau)$ can be obtained from $U_{ij}^{(m)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t - \tau)$ by applying the following differential operator [2, 3, 13]:

$$P_{ik}[\bullet, (\mathbf{y})] = \lambda n_i(\mathbf{y}) \frac{\partial[\bullet]}{\partial y_k} + \mu \left[\delta_{ik} \frac{\partial[\bullet]}{\partial \mathbf{n}(\mathbf{y})} + n_k(\mathbf{y}) \frac{\partial[\bullet]}{\partial y_i} \right]. \quad (2)$$

Applying the differential operator (2) to the Somigliana dynamic identity (1) we obtain the components of the traction vector in terms of boundary displacements and tractions for both half-spaces:

$$p_j^{(m)}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \int_{\Gamma^{(m)}} \int (p_i^{(m)}(\mathbf{y}, \tau) K_{ij}^{(m)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t - \tau) - u_i^{(m)}(\mathbf{y}, \tau) F_{ij}^{(m)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t - \tau)) dy d\tau, \quad (3)$$

$$\mathbf{x} \in \Omega^{(m)}, \quad t \in T,$$

where the integral kernels $K_{ij}^{(m)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t - \tau)$ and $F_{ij}^{(m)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t - \tau)$ are obtained from the fundamental Green tensor by applying the differential operator (2).

For the limiting case $\mathbf{x} \rightarrow \Gamma^{(m)}$, taking into account the assumed relatively smooth distribution of traction on regular surfaces $\Gamma^{(1)}$ and $\Gamma^{(2)}$, the following representation of the traction vector at the interface can be obtained from Eq. (3):

$$\frac{1}{2} p_j^{(m)}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \int_{\Gamma^{(m)}} \int (p_i^{(m)}(\mathbf{y}, \tau) K_{ij}^{(m)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t - \tau) - u_i^{(m)}(\mathbf{y}, \tau) F_{ij}^{(m)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t - \tau)) dy d\tau, \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{x} \in \Gamma^{(m)}$, $t \in T$.

Finally, the system of boundary integral equations takes the form:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2} g_j^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}, t) &= \int_{\Gamma^{(1)cr}} \int_{\Gamma^{(1)cr}} (g_i^{(1)}(\mathbf{y}, \tau) K_{ij}^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t - \tau) - u_i^{(1)}(\mathbf{y}, \tau) F_{ij}^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t - \tau)) d\mathbf{y} d\tau \\ &+ \int_{\Gamma^*} \int_{\Gamma^*} (u_i^*(\mathbf{y}, \tau) F_{ij}^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t - \tau) - p_i^*(\mathbf{y}, \tau) K_{ij}^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t - \tau)) d\mathbf{y} d\tau, \quad \mathbf{x} \in \Gamma^{(1)cr}, \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2} g_j^{(2)}(\mathbf{x}, t) &= \int_{\Gamma^{(2)cr}} \int_{\Gamma^{(2)cr}} (g_i^{(2)}(\mathbf{y}, \tau) K_{ij}^{(2)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t - \tau) - u_i^{(2)}(\mathbf{y}, \tau) F_{ij}^{(2)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t - \tau)) d\mathbf{y} d\tau \\ &- \int_{\Gamma^*} \int_{\Gamma^*} (u_i^*(\mathbf{y}, \tau) F_{ij}^{(2)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t - \tau) - p_i^*(\mathbf{y}, \tau) K_{ij}^{(2)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t - \tau)) d\mathbf{y} d\tau, \quad \mathbf{x} \in \Gamma^{(2)cr}, \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\Gamma^{(1)cr}} \int_{\Gamma^{(1)cr}} g_i^{(1)}(\mathbf{y}, \tau) K_{ij}^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t - \tau) d\mathbf{y} d\tau &= \frac{1}{2} p_j^*(\mathbf{x}, t) + \int_{\Gamma^{(1)cr}} \int_{\Gamma^{(1)cr}} u_i^{(1)}(\mathbf{y}, \tau) F_{ij}^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t - \tau) d\mathbf{y} d\tau \\ &- \int_{\Gamma^*} \int_{\Gamma^*} (u_i^*(\mathbf{y}, \tau) F_{ij}^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t - \tau) - p_i^*(\mathbf{y}, \tau) K_{ij}^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t - \tau)) d\mathbf{y} d\tau, \quad \mathbf{x} \in \Gamma^*, \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\Gamma^{(2)cr}} \int_{\Gamma^{(2)cr}} g_i^{(2)}(\mathbf{y}, \tau) K_{ij}^{(2)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t - \tau) d\mathbf{y} d\tau &= \frac{1}{2} p_j^*(\mathbf{x}, t) + \int_{\Gamma^{(2)cr}} \int_{\Gamma^{(2)cr}} u_i^{(2)}(\mathbf{y}, \tau) F_{ij}^{(2)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t - \tau) d\mathbf{y} d\tau \\ &+ \int_{\Gamma^*} \int_{\Gamma^*} (u_i^*(\mathbf{y}, \tau) F_{ij}^{(2)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t - \tau) - p_i^*(\mathbf{y}, \tau) K_{ij}^{(2)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t - \tau)) d\mathbf{y} d\tau, \quad \mathbf{x} \in \Gamma^*, \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where $\mathbf{g}^{(m)}(\mathbf{x}, t)$, $\mathbf{x} \in \Gamma^{(m)cr}$ ($m=1,2$) are known traction vectors at the opposite crack faces, which are determined by the external load.

We also introduced the new variables, $u_i^*(\mathbf{x}, t)$ and $p_i^*(\mathbf{x}, t)$:

$$\begin{aligned} u_i^*(\mathbf{x}, t) &= u_i^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}, t), \quad p_i^*(\mathbf{x}, t) = -p_i^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}, t), \quad \mathbf{x} \in \Gamma^{(1)*}, t \in \Gamma, \\ u_i^*(\mathbf{x}, t) &= u_i^{(2)}(\mathbf{x}, t), \quad p_i^*(\mathbf{x}, t) = p_i^{(2)}(\mathbf{x}, t), \quad \mathbf{x} \in \Gamma^{(2)*}, t \in \Gamma. \end{aligned}$$

Note that in the present study the form of the resulting boundary integral equations system (5)–(8) differs significantly from the corresponding integral system in [9–11]. The resulting system of boundary integral equations becomes simpler, it does not contain integral kernels $U_{ij}^{(m)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t - \tau)$ and $W_{ij}^{(m)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t - \tau)$. The further algebraic manipulations (i.e. summation and subtraction of the corresponding integral equations) are also unnecessary, therefore the system of boundary integral equations does not

contain residuals of all integral kernels and the corresponding matrix of linear algebraic equations becomes sparser. For example, in the case of the collocation method with a piecewise continuous approximation used in this study, the number of non-zero elements of the matrix of linear algebraic equations decreases by $8N_{out}(N_{in} - 1)$, where N_{out} and N_{in} are the numbers of boundary elements located on the bonding interface and crack surface respectively. Consequently the total number of integrals over boundary elements, required to be computed in order to solve the problem, decreases even further, by $4N_{out}(4N_{in} + 4N_{out})$, which results in the significant acceleration of the numerical solution of the problem. On average, the solution time decreases by 40–50%. The stability of the obtained solution also increases, especially for the higher frequencies of external loading and for the cases with considerable difference between mechanical properties of adjoining half-spaces.

For the case of harmonic loading with the frequency $\omega = 2\pi/T$, which is considered in the paper, tractions and displacements are harmonic functions and can be presented as follows:

$$f(\bullet, t) = \text{Re}(f(\bullet)e^{i\omega t}), \quad f(\bullet) = \frac{\omega}{2\pi} \int_0^T f(\bullet, t)e^{-i\omega t} dt.$$

Then the system of boundary integral equations (5)–(8) can be rewritten as:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2} g_j^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}) - \int_{\Gamma^{(m)\text{cr}}} g_i^{(1)}(\mathbf{y}) K_{ij}^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \omega) d\mathbf{y} = & - \int_{\Gamma^{(m)\text{cr}}} u_i^{(1)}(\mathbf{y}) F_{ij}^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \omega) d\mathbf{y} \\ + \int_{\Gamma^*} (u_i^*(\mathbf{y}) F_{ij}^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \omega) - p_i^*(\mathbf{y}) K_{ij}^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \omega)) d\mathbf{y}, \quad \mathbf{x} \in \Gamma^{(1)\text{cr}}, \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2} g_j^{(2)}(\mathbf{x}) - \int_{\Gamma^{(m)\text{cr}}} g_i^{(2)}(\mathbf{y}) K_{ij}^{(2)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \omega) d\mathbf{y} = & - \int_{\Gamma^{(m)\text{cr}}} u_i^{(2)}(\mathbf{y}) F_{ij}^{(2)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \omega) d\mathbf{y} \\ - \int_{\Gamma^*} (u_i^*(\mathbf{y}) F_{ij}^{(2)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \omega) - p_i^*(\mathbf{y}) K_{ij}^{(2)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \omega)) d\mathbf{y}, \quad \mathbf{x} \in \Gamma^{(2)\text{cr}}, \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\Gamma^{(1)\text{cr}}} g_i^{(1)}(\mathbf{y}) K_{ij}^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \omega) d\mathbf{y} = \frac{1}{2} p_j^*(\mathbf{x}) + \int_{\Gamma^{(1)\text{cr}}} u_i^{(1)}(\mathbf{y}) F_{ij}^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \omega) d\mathbf{y} \\ - \int_{\Gamma^*} (u_i^*(\mathbf{y}) F_{ij}^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \omega) - p_i^*(\mathbf{y}) K_{ij}^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \omega)) d\mathbf{y}, \quad \mathbf{x} \in \Gamma^*, \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\int_{\Gamma^{(2)\text{cr}}} g_i^{(2)}(\mathbf{y}) K_{ij}^{(2)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \omega) d\mathbf{y} &= \frac{1}{2} p_j^*(\mathbf{x}) + \int_{\Gamma^{(2)\text{cr}}} u_i^{(2)}(\mathbf{y}) F_{ij}^{(2)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \omega) d\mathbf{y} \\
+ \int_{\Gamma^*} (u_i^*(\mathbf{y}) F_{ij}^{(2)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \omega) - p_i^*(\mathbf{y}) K_{ij}^{(2)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \omega)) d\mathbf{y}, \quad \mathbf{x} \in \Gamma^*.
\end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

Note that due to the presence of non-integrable singularities in the integral kernels $F_{ij}^{(m)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \omega)$, whose rank exceeds the dimension of the integration region, the corresponding hypersingular integrals of the system of boundary integral equations (9)–(12) are treated in the sense of the Hadamard finite part [11, 13–15].

NUMERICAL RESULTS

As a numerical example let us consider an incident time-harmonic tension-compression wave of the intensity p_0 propagates in the normal direction to the interface of a linear crack with length $2R$. Poisson's ratio for the materials are specified as $\nu^{(1)} = 0.3$ and $\nu^{(2)} = 0.25$, and the ratios of their Young's moduli and material densities are specified as $E^{(1)}/E^{(2)} = 2.0$ and $\rho^{(1)}/\rho^{(2)} = 3.0$, respectively.

The piecewise constant approximation of the known and unknown functions was used to solve the problem numerically. The normal and tangential tractions and displacements at the bonding interface are given in Figures 2 and 3, respectively, for the wave number $k_2^{(1)}R = 0.1$, where $k_2^{(1)} = \omega/c_2^{(1)}$, $c_2^{(1)}$ is the velocity of the transversal wave in the upper half-space. Results are normalized by the factor $2\mu_0/Rp_0$, where p_0 is the stress amplitude of the incident wave and μ_0 is specified in [7].

The solution is symmetric with respect to the centre of the crack and the Sommerfeld radiation-type condition is satisfied at the infinity, i.e. the tractions and displacements at the bonding interface decrease gradually with increase in the distance to the crack.

CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, the boundary integral equations method was applied to the problem of an infinite crack between two dissimilar elastic half-spaces under harmonic loading. The distributions of the displacements and tractions at the bimaterial interface were obtained and analysed.

It must be noted that in reality the opposite crack faces interact with each other under dynamic loading. The nature of contact interaction between two opposite crack faces is very complex. Under deformation of the material, the initial contact area will change in time. The shape and the contact area would be unknown beforehand and must be determined as a part of solution. The complexity of the problem is further compounded by the fact that the contact behaviour is very sensitive to the properties of two contacting surfaces and the external loading [13, 14]. Considering this interaction is the natural next stage of this research.

a)

b)

Figure 2 Normal (a) and tangential (b) tractions on the bonding interface

Figure 3 Normal (a) and tangential (b) displacements on the bonding interface

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